

Fungi Associated with Postharvest Fruit Rots of Orange in local Market of El-Beida City, Libya

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ABSTRACT:

Citrus is one of the most widely grown plants in the world; however, it is affected by many types of fruit rot diseases after harvesting. Orange fruits showing rot symptoms that are displayed for sale local market were collected and examined for the presence of the pathogenic fungi. Three species of fungi *Alternaria alternata*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Penicillium digitatum* were found to be associated with fruit rots of orange. *P. digitatum* was the most frequently isolated and *A. niger* was the least isolated 63.9% and 11.1% respectively. All isolated fungi were pathogenic to the different fruits when pathogenicity tests were carried out. They produced same symptoms and signs as observed in the original spoil orange fruits before isolation. All fungal isolates were able to re-infect the healthy citrus fruits with the exception of *Alternaria* which was weakly to grow and produce spoilage condition on the inoculated healthy orange fruits after five days. *P. digitatum* as the most pathogenic inducing a rot diameter of 2.4cm within 5 days of inoculation.

Keyword: *Citrus species, Fungal species, fruit rot, Pathogenicity test, Libya.*

INTRODUCTION

Fruits and vegetables are exposed to contamination by microbes through contact with soil, dust and water and by handling at harvest or during postharvest processing. This makes them to harbor a wide range of microorganisms including plant and human pathogens [1]. Differences in microbial profiles of diverse fruits and vegetables result could be due to varying factors including resident microflora in the soil, application of non-resident microflora through animal manures, sewage or irrigation water, transportation and handling by individual retailers [2]. Citrus is the second largest fruit crop worldwide [3] and it is one of the foremost export fruit crops in Libya and in the rest of the world. It is primarily valued for its fruit, which is either consumed (sour orange, sweet orange, tangerine, grapefruit, etc.) or used in processing industry. All species have traditional medicinal value. Citrus has many other uses including animal fodder and craft and fuel wood [4]. In addition, their essential oils are used in the cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries [5].

Postharvest diseases play a major role in reducing the quantity and quality of citrus. Postharvest fungal decay may cause significant losses to the citrus industry worldwide [6]. Injuries on citrus fruit caused during harvest, provide entries to wound pathogens, including *Alternaria* spp., *Aspergillus* spp., *Colletotrichum* spp., *Geotrichum* spp., *Penicillium* spp. and *Rhizopus* spp. causal agents of mold. The mold invades the fruit much more rapidly and predominates in mixed infections, causing approximately 60-80% of decay [6,7,8,9]. *Candida tropicalis*, *saccaromyces cerevisiae* and species of *Rhizopus*, *Penicillium*, *Aspergillus*, *Alternaria*, and *Mucor* were associated with orange fruits [10]. Baria et al. [11] reported *Aspergillus* spp., *Fusarium* spp., *Penicillium* spp. and *Rhizopus* sp. were responsible for postharvest losses of citrus in different market of Anand, India. El-Gali [12] has also reported *P. italicum* and *P. digitatum* on citrus. The study was conducted to isolate and identify the fungi associated with the fruit rots of orange fruits in local market of El-Beida city.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Fruit source and isolation, identification of fungi. Orange fruit both fresh and those found with symptoms of infection were collected from local market in El-Beida city, Libya. All infected fruits and rotted were stored in clean polyethylene bags. The healthy samples were also stored separately, and brought to the Microbiology laboratory at Agriculture college University, Omer, Al-Mukhtar, for further studies. A total of 30 selected fungal infected fruits were purchased. The diseased samples were first surface sterilized by washing under running tap water to remove dirt such as sand. A flamed blade was used to cut partly diseased and partly healthy portion of the sample, the cut portions were then surface sterilized using 1% sodium hypochlorite after which they were rinsed in successive changes of sterile distilled water.

Segments (3-5 mm) of tissues placed on previously prepared potato sucrose agar (PSA) in Petri dishes and incubated at 25 ± 1°C for 5 days under 12 h photoperiod. The purified isolates were maintained on PSA slants for further studies. The pathogen that appeared was primarily identified up to species level using cultural and morphological features under the light microscopic [13].

Pathogenicity of fungi on fruits.

Healthy fruits of similar size, color and maturity were sterilized by exposing them in 1% sodium hypochlorite. Pathogenicity test were carried out according to Koch's postulates; Two techniques were employed for each fungal culture. First, an artificially wounded (1 mm wide and 2 mm deep) with sterile needles in the middle of each fruit. One 3 mm mycelial disk of 7 days old culture of each isolated fungus was cut from the edge of the colony and put on each wound. Second, a hole was bored into each of surface sterilized fruits with a 5 mm cork borer. One 3 mm mycelial disk was put in the hole (Fig. 1). Control treatment were inoculated by placing a PSA plug without fungal mycelia on each wound. Five orange fruits were inoculated with each of the isolates and this experiment was replicated three times. The inoculated fruits were placed on tray packs in plastic boxes containing moistened filter

paper, covered with cling-films, and stored at 25°C with three replicates of 5 fruits for each treatment. After 5 days, the radii of rotted symptoms were measured from inoculation site on the fruits surface [14].

Host range.

The pathogen was artificially (Fig. 1) inoculated on different plant

species for their sensitivity to fungi isolates to know the host range of various plant species including lime (*Citrus latifolia*), lemon (*C. limone*), sour orange (*C. aurantium*), sweet orange (*C. sinensis*) and *Citrus* sp. (navel). The inoculated fruits were kept under observation up to 7 days for any symptom development as per descriptions in materials and methods.

Figure 1. Wounded and inoculated for citrus in pathogenicity test

Results

Three fungal species belonging to three genera were found associated with postharvest deterioration of citrus fruits in El-Beida, Libya. These are *Alternaria alternata*, *Aspergillus niger*, and *Penicillium digitatum* (Fig. 2).

A. alternata. Typical cultural and morphological characteristics are shown in Figure 4. On PSA plates colonies were velvety. The isolates first developed grayish with a very thin white margin, and cottony texture (Fig. 4-a). Colonies later developed color, the colors became dark olive as fungal age increased (Fig. 4-b). conidia, which are large, ovoid to obclavate, dark-colored (melanized), multicellular with longitudinal and transverse septations (phaeodictyospores). Conidia are produced in single or branched chains on short conidiophores (Fig 5-b) and showed 3-8 transverse and longitudinal septa.

A. niger. Growth on PSA, its white to yellow mat later bearing black conidia, surface velvety to cottony. Mycelium - septate and hyaline with unbranched conidiophores. Conidial heads are dark brown to black, radiate and biseriate with metulae twice as long as the phialides. Conidia brown and rough-walled.

P. digitatum: On PDA, the fungus formed radial colonies of white airy mycelia, and the substrate mycelium was olive green with a clear zone observed from the bottom of the plate (Fig. 2). Conidiophores of the fungus are showing two-stage branching, cylindrical phialides and chains of single-celled conidia (Fig. 2 Pd.).

Figure 2. Fungal colonies on PSA medium (upper) and conidia (below).

The most frequently isolated fungus was *P. digitatum* with a percentage incidence of 63.9% while *A. niger* was the least encountered fungus (11.1%). Similarly, the total colony count of *P. digitatum* (29) was higher in comparison to those of other fungi (Fig. 4).

Figure 3. Frequency and count of fungi associated with Fruit Rot of orange

In a survey of citrus, we reported the appearance of novel symptoms of *A. alternata*. These symptoms include black spots on fruit, ranging from a single lesion to lesions that cover more than 50% of the fruit surface (Fig. 4b1,2) and black rot restricted to internal fruit tissues. Another fungus that is also isolated from citrus is *Aspergillus niger*: symptoms on fruits appeared in two forms: spherical depressed spots. The damage is restricted to the peel surface while the edible tissue remains unaffected. The heart rot decay (Fig. 4a1,2).

The symptoms which observed in Libya on the nearly-matured fruits as soft water-soaked area. Such area gradually increases in size and turn white with translucent margins and covered with concentric zones of white colour mycelia embedded in the disease tissues (Fig. 4.c1) or covered with fungal growth as a mass of spores (Fig. 4. C2). One of the pathogenic fungi that are associated with fruit rot of citrus is *p. digitatum*.

Pathogenicity and host range.

From the pathogenicity test, all the fungal isolates caused rot on healthy fruits. All the isolated fungi were pathogenic on inoculated citrus fruits. The result of the pathogenicity test revealed that all the fungi originally isolated from diseased orange induce similar disease symptoms when inoculated on healthy orange.

However, the degree of infection differed substantially among the

fungal species and types of citrus fruit. *P. digitatum* being the most pathogenic producing a rot diameter of 2.4cm within 5 days of inoculation under ambient environmental conditions, while *A.*

alternata was least pathogenic fungi. All varieties were different in susceptibility to infection with tested fungi, whereas lemon, sour orange and navel orange were most susceptible (Table 1).

Figure 4. Different symptoms on citrus fruits.

Table 1: Pathogenicity and rot severity of fungal species associated on five different fruit citrus

Fungi isolates	Host	Diameter of rot (cm)	Rot severity (%)
<i>A. alternata</i>	<i>Citrus latifolia</i>	0	0
	<i>C. limone</i>	0	0
	<i>C. aurantium</i>	1	13.3
	<i>C. sinensis</i>	0.5	6.7
	<i>Citrus sp. (navel)</i>	0	0
<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. latifolia</i>	0.5	13.3
	<i>C. limone</i>	0.5	20
	<i>C. aurantium</i>	0	0
	<i>C. sinensis</i>	0	0
	<i>Citrus sp. (navel)</i>	0.5	20
<i>P. digitatum</i>	<i>C. latifolia</i>	0.5	6.7
	<i>C. limone</i>	0.8	33.3
	<i>C. aurantium</i>	2.3	46.6
	<i>C. sinensis</i>	0.8	33.3
	<i>Citrus sp. (navel)</i>	2.4	46.6

Discussion.

Fruits are affected by a wide array of microorganisms causing its decay. Soft or pulpy fruits undergo a soft or wet rot because of the abundance of water in their tissue [15]. The post-harvest fungal diseases are responsible for biodeterioration of fruits pulp [16,17]. The results obtained from this study have indicated that citrus which were sold in the local market in El-Beida city were contaminated by fungal agents. Isolates such as (*A. alternta*, *A. niger*, and *P. digitatum*) where identified. This is in agreement with the findings of Ojo et al. [8] who reported several species of fungal pathogens found associated with citrus (*Aspergillus* spp. and *Penicillium* spp.). Also Embaby et al. [18] surveyed markets located at Beheira and Qalyoubia Governorates region, Egypt and reported that *Alternaria citri*, *Botryodiblotia theobromae*, *Fusarium* sp., *Penicillium digitatum* and *P. italicum* were associated with citrus fruits. Ammar and El-Nagar [9] confirmed that *Alternara* spp. is one of pathogenic fungi in fruits after harvest and storage. *P. digitatum* was the most dominant on citrus fruit after harvesting in Libya [12,19]. Fruits and vegetables are susceptible to pathogenic attack due to their low PH, high moisture content and nutrient composition. These make them rot and unfit for consumption Pathogenicity tests showed that all pathogens isolated affected all species of citrus. The different effect may be

attributed to the effect of sugar and nutritive content of all varieties on the growth of the fungal pathogens. During pathogenicity it was observed that the rate of disintegration of the citrus variety infected with *P. digitatum* was faster than that of the citrus variety infected with other fungi. But due to insufficient data it cannot be clearly ascertained if the real cause of this rapid deterioration is due to external or internal factors around or within the fruits. The market value of fruits are reduced as a result of pathogen infestation. Their presence in these food produce also constitute health risks.

Conclusion.

The results of this experiment showed fruits were attacked by fungi causing different types of disease. the rotten orange fruit decay with various types of fungi, The fruits used in this study are not cultivated in the city but are transported to from distant villages in locally woven baskets and sacks under weather conditions that encourage the incubation of these contaminating microorganisms. It is therefore important that both the farmer who harvests the fruits into bags for transportation, the marketers and consumers take necessary precaution in preventing contamination and also try to create an environment that will not encourage the growth or multiplication of microorganisms which may be produces

mycotoxin and cause harm to the consumers.

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